

Preparation of xanthan and carbopol model fluids

Step	Task	Images	Comment
<p>Document title: Preparation of xanthan and carbopol model fluids</p> <p>Laboratory location: University of Stavanger (UiS)</p> <p>Objective: This procedure describes the laboratory method used to prepare xanthan- and carbopol-based model fluids for the experimental work in this thesis. It includes weighing, mixing, additive incorporation, labeling, and storage of the prepared fluids.</p> <p>Assumptions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The required quantities and concentrations have been calculated • Sugar, xanthan, carbopol, and 5% NaOH are available 			
<p>Fill liquid 1 (water)</p>			
<p>1.</p>	<p>Weigh an empty beaker glass vessel (typically a 1000 mL beaker). Use the balance tray located in the fume hood. To calibrate the scale, press “Tare”.</p> <p>It will vary, but it should be approximately 0 g.</p>		
<p>2.</p>	<p>Fill with tap water until you have approximately the desired amount based on the Excel file. It is not very important what the mL reading shows, but fill the beaker accordingly. Then wait a little until it becomes clear. The water may look “dirty” at first, so wait a bit.</p>		<p>After some time, the water will clear up. Use cold water, since it has been observed that with lukewarm or warm water, the weight gradually decreases as the water evaporates. Be</p>

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			<p>consistent to use cold water</p>
3.	<p>Fill the beaker until it approaches the desired mass in grams, using the scale as your reference rather than the mL markings. Do not fill to the brim; slightly underfill it so you can use a pipette afterward.</p>		
4.	<p>Find a disposable pipette to achieve an approximately accurate mass in grams. See the pictures for where to find it.</p>		<p>The pipette can be found by the lab coats.</p>

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5.	Use the pipette to reach the desired amount. For example, the picture shows that the desired amount is 250 g. Remember to record the weight.		It is recommended to wait briefly before recording the measurement, as fluctuations may occur.
Mixing the liquids together			
1.	<p>Place an empty beaker/cup on the scale and press “Tare.”</p> <p>Xanthan:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measure the desired amount of xanthan powder. • Record the xanthan weight. • If desired: Find a new empty beaker/cup, press tare, and measure the sugar. • Record the sugar weight. <p>Carbopol:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measure the desired amount of carbopol powder. • Record the carbopol weight. • If desired: Find a new empty beaker/cup, press tare, and measure the 5% NaOH. • Record the 5% NaOH weight. <p>Information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sugar is intended to increase the density of the xanthan. • 5% NaOH is intended to neutralize the pH of the carbopol and create a gel structure. 		It is recommended to wait briefly before recording the measurement, as fluctuations in the scale reading may occur due to movement of the liquid, which can disturb the measurement. Therefore, the reading should be taken only after the liquid has become completely still.

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2.	Close the draft shield as shown in the picture.		
Use a blender.			
1.	Rinse the hand blender with water and dry with paper.		
2.	Place the beaker containing the mixed liquid near the blender.		
3.	Place the blender in the holder and raise it so that there is enough space for the beaker underneath.		

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4.	Use the key shown in the image to lock/unlock the blender.		The red circle shows where to insert the screwdriver.
5.	Tighten it while the hand blender is inside the beaker. It should be in contact with the liquid.		<p>Try to position the hand blender well down into the liquid. From experience, it did not mix properly when it was placed too high, as shown in picture 2.</p> <p>Make sure the hand blender is centered so it does not hit the glass while spinning.</p> <p>You can simply move the beaker around to center the hand blender, as shown in picture 3.</p>

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6.	Turn on the hand blender by pressing the button marked with a circle and an “I” symbol in the middle of the circle, as shown by the red circle in the picture.		
7.	<p>Xanthan: Increase the speed slowly to 600 rpm.</p> <p>Carbopol: Increase the speed slowly to 800 rpm.</p>		If it does not rotate, try turning it to the right where the finger is pointing and see if it starts rotating. The picture shows how to turn it and where to place your finger and move it. The wheel is used to adjust the rpm speed.
8.	<p>Xanthan: Add the measured xanthan powder together with the sugar. Mix for 10 minutes.</p> <p>Carbopol Add only the measured carbopol, not the 5% NaOH. Mix for one hour.</p>		The mixture should be stirred at a speed sufficient to create a visible vortex (“tornado”). If no vortex forms, the mixer position may be adjusted slightly upward, or the rotational speed may be increased gradually until a stable vortex is obtained.

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9.	<p>For carbopol: After 1 hour of mixing, add the 5% NaOH and mix for 10 minutes.</p>		
10.	After mixing, press the “I” button to turn it off.		
11.	<p>Loosen the hand blender using a screwdriver, raise it to allow removal of the beaker, and tighten it again in the adjusted position. Place paper underneath to catch any spills during handling. After the liquid has been transferred to a beaker, rinse the original container.</p>		
Store the liquid you have mixed			

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12.	Pour the liquid into a container with a lid.		
13.	Find the sheet of labels. It is located by the door, next to the door leading into the lab.		
14.	Write the name of the person who prepared it, the amount of liquid, the percentage concentration, and the date.		

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15.	Peel off the label and attach it to the beaker containing the liquid mixture.		
16.	Put the sheet of labels back by the door.		
17.	Place the sample in a clearly designated location together with the other prepared fluids intended for subsequent use, so that it can be easily identified later.		
18.	Now wash the hand blender with dish soap and a brush, and place it next to the machine with paper underneath. Use gloves and wipe up any spills if necessary.		
19.	Check that the draft shield is closed and that the balance is turned off.		